

The SOAR Telescope in the Time-Domain and Multi-Messenger Astronomy Era

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Introduction

Astronomy is living through exciting and groundbreaking times. The advent of facilities that search for transients and measure time-variable objects across all the sky, such as the [Zwicky Transient Facility \(ZTF\)](#), [Gaia](#), and the upcoming [Vera C. Rubin Observatory](#) with its Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), together with the gravitational wave instruments [LIGO](#), [VIRGO](#), and now [KAGRA](#), is positioning Time-Domain Astronomy (TDA) and Multi-Messenger Astrophysics (MMA) among the forefront areas of astrophysics for the next decade. Studies of the content and nature—including the identification of possible potential collision threats—of small bodies in our Solar System, exoplanet discoveries, studies of stellar variability in all its forms, explosive and violent phenomena such as supernovae (SNe), gamma ray bursts, and mergers of dense stellar remnants such as black holes and neutron stars, using variable stars and SNe in other galaxies to gauge the cosmic ladder, and observing active galactic nuclei all illustrate that the range of science spanned by TDA and MMA is both broad and exciting.

TDA also brings a scale of data management and mining not seen before. ZTF is producing thousands of alerts per night, covering ~ 3760 square degrees/hour of the sky visible from Mt. Palomar, to median 5σ depths of $g \sim 20.8$ and $r \sim 20.6$ mag (AB magnitudes; [1]). The LSST will map the entire sky accessible from Cerro Pachón, Chile, in the *ugrizy* filters to a 5σ single-visit depth of $r \sim 24$ mag (AB), producing about 10^6 alerts per night. Although the LSST will make many visits—typically hundreds—and the resulting data can be co-added, for most transient phenomena, whether time-variable or moving objects, the relevant sensitivity is set by a single visit. The LSST has well-defined science goals that will be achieved with the survey data alone: an inventory of the Solar System, Mapping the Milky Way, Exploring the Transient Optical Sky, and Probing Dark Energy and Dark Matter.

However, full exploitation of the LSST data products will depend on the ability to carry out complementary and follow-up observations that will provide confirmation, characterization, and further study of transients and variable objects [2]. The need for LSST follow-up was also recognized by the National Research Council (NRC), commissioned by the National Science Foundation (NSF). In *Optimizing the U.S. Ground-Based Optical and Infrared System* [3], the NRC presented a series of recommendations for the national ground-based optical-infrared (OIR) system, advising that NSF support the development of the ground-based facilities needed to optimize LSST follow-up science. The report targeted the synergy between the Gemini telescopes, the Southern Astrophysical Research (SOAR) Telescope, the Víctor M. Blanco 4m Telescope, and the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST). LSST and discussed how existing or new instruments and operation modes can be implemented and managed in ways that maximize the scientific return. A subsequent review of the NSF-funded Gemini, Blanco, and SOAR telescopes [4] reinforced this conclusion.

Time-Domain and Multi-Messenger Astronomy at SOAR
SOAR is particularly well-suited for LSST follow-up. First, it is co-located with Vera C. Rubin Observatory (Figure 1) and therefore has access to the same targets and experiences the same observing conditions. Second, SOAR has a suite of permanently installed optical and infrared instruments, both

Figure 1. *Upper panel:* Panoramic view of Cerro Pachón with the SOAR, Gemini South, and Vera C. Rubin observatories. (Credit: LSST Project/NSF/AURA/C. Briceño) *Lower left panel:* SOAR building under the Milky Way. (Credit: CTIO/NOIRLab/C. Briceño) *Lower right panel:* SOAR 4.1m telescope. (Credit: SOAR/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

Figure 2. Spectral sequence of AT2018cow. The phase is measured relative to the epoch of discovery, MJD=58285.44 [20]. (Adapted from [10], with permission)

imagers and spectrographs, available to be used within minutes. Built for excellent image quality across a relatively small field (less than 10 arcminutes in diameter for all instruments), SOAR can reach the LSST single-visit limit (5σ) of $r \sim 24$ (AB), in ~ 90 s in imaging mode in the g , r filters and can obtain $\text{SNR} \sim 5$ optical spectra at $R \sim 1000$ down to $r \sim 22$ in 1 h. There will be a significant number of LSST targets accessible to 4m-class telescopes such as SOAR; in particular, the brighter ones will be within reach of a broad range of astronomical facilities, as noted, for example, in the 2015 NRC report to the National Academies [3].

But even before Rubin Observatory comes online, SOAR has been playing an important role in TDA and improving

its instruments and operations to enhance its capabilities in the LSST era. The high level of experience and quality of the staff operating the SOAR telescope at the mountain, forming a cohesive team with the support scientists at La Serena, has allowed us to become one of the premier facilities for transient science, including characterization of Small Solar System bodies and Near Earth Objects [5], [6], [7] and gravitational wave (GW) follow-up (e.g., [8], [9]). The SOAR Target of Opportunity (ToO) policy allows quick handling of requests for a variety of fast-evolving or young transients, including GW alerts, that require rapid response, while taking into account the science needs of the astronomer scheduled for the night of the ToO interrupt.

SOAR has recently further shown its effectiveness as a TDA and MMA tool by providing optical and near-IR data of excellent quality in breakthrough discoveries, such as the follow-up campaign of the rare, bright, and fast-evolving transient AT 2018cow [10], powered by a non-standard central engine. The observations obtained with the Goodman spectrograph at SOAR were key for securing a set of early, well time-sampled spectra (Figure 2). Other recent examples are the near-IR spectrum of the rapidly evolving calcium-rich transient SN 2019ehk [11], obtained during the commissioning of the TSpec near-IR spectrograph at SOAR, or the early optical and near-IR spectra (Figure 3) of the Type Ic SN 2020oi [12], which enabled the study of the outermost layers of this SN explosion in exquisite detail [13]. Both objects exploded in the nearby galaxy Messier 100 within the course of a year. The high-throughput Goodman spectrograph, reaching down to ~ 21 – 22 mag objects in ~ 1 h, and SOAR's rapid response to ToO alerts have been key for the follow-up of possible electromagnetic counterparts of GW alerts during the O3 LIGO/VIRGO run in 2019. Various research groups have published their latest results, including lessons learned from this campaign, highlighting the role of SOAR [14], [15], [16].

Preparing for the LSST Era

Looking ahead, we are carrying out a number of upgrades and improvements to both SOAR instruments and operations. Starting in late 2017, we embarked on an ambitious automation plan, which has positioned SOAR as one of the founding partners of the Astronomical Event Observatory Network (AEON; [17]) and the pathfinder facility for incorporating 4m-class and larger facilities in a

Figure 3. Early spectra of SN 2020oi obtained with the Goodman and TSpec spectrographs on SOAR. The phase is the time relative from the estimated epoch of the SN explosion. (Adapted from [13])

future LSST follow-up system. With AEON we have started running a highly automated queue using the Goodman spectrograph, on select nights. This degree of automation also benefits all users, beyond AEON, by providing observers of classically scheduled nights web-based tools for queueing their targets and automating many steps of the spectrograph operation, with the resulting gain in efficiency and reliability of data acquisition. We are also actively developing data-reduction tools. We have implemented a Python-based spectroscopic pipeline for the Goodman spectrograph [18], which makes extensive use of Astropy modules and libraries, with extensive documentation written following best practices and standards. We are currently developing a real-time version of the Goodman spectroscopic pipeline, accessible via a web browser (no software to download and install), that produces fully reduced 1D, wavelength-calibrated spectra seconds after the raw data are written to disk [19]. This new tool provides users with real-time visualization of their reduced spectra, allowing them to make rapid decisions on whether to obtain more data on the same target or change to another object. We expect these and other ongoing efforts will position SOAR among the forefront 4m-class facilities for TDA, MMA, and a wide range of science cases in the next decade.

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